

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI): MAKING AMERICA INTELLIGENT AGAIN?

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Abstract. *‘Winning the Race: America’s AI Action Plan’ is stated to be the US “roadmap to victory” in the “AI race”. In the 24 page AI Plan, Joe Biden is the only person singled out for mention (n=2). China is the only country singled out for mention (n=6). The AI Plan is framed as a military-esque project replete with ‘victory’ and ‘global domination’ as goals. The AI Plan is populated with multiple mentions of ‘malicious actors’ and ‘adversaries’. The American conquistadors are to ensure that ‘American values’ are embedded in AI, while “Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion” (DEI), and “climate change” are not.*

Keywords: *Artificial intelligence, artificial stupidity (AS), American imperialism, global domination, conquest, race.*

The Plan: ‘Winning the Race: America’s AI Action Plan’, Executive Office of the President of the United States, The White House, Washington, July 2025, 24 pp [1] is about technology overreach and domination rather than isolationism (Fig.1). The Plan is available at: <www.whitehouse.gov>.

The ‘AI’ of the Plan is ‘artificial intelligence’. Customers may be more familiar with the artificial stupidity (AS) of customer service chatbots [2]. The Introduction to the AI Plan pulls no punches: “The United States is in a race to achieve global dominance in artificial intelligence (AI)” [M J Kratsios, D O Sacks & M A Rubio in 1, p.1].

The AI Plan boldly declares that: “America must have the most powerful AI systems in the world” [p.3]. There are three “Pillars” to the AI Plan, viz: “I. Accelerate AI Innovation”; “II. Build American AI Infrastructure”; “III. Lead in International Diplomacy and Security” [p.ii]. Donald Trump declares that: “it is a national security imperative for the United States to achieve and maintain unquestioned and unchallenged global technological dominance” [p.i].

Global domination

You have been warned! America’s Action Plan for artificial intelligence (AI) is all about “winning the race” [Title page of 1] and global domination [Trump in 1, p.i]. The Plan is not about spreading the joy, nor spreading the wealth. It’s not about fostering world peace and harmony. The AI Plan is unabashedly about America winning above others, and not about making the world a better place. As Trump declares: “transformative technologies such as artificial intelligence ... have the potential to reshape the global balance of power” [p.i].

Victory

“The AI race is America’s to win, and the Action Plan is our roadmap to victory” [Kratsios et al in 1, p.2]. There is the opportunity for the US to “reap broad economic and military benefits” [p.2]. A curious benefit identified in the AI Plan is that American AI will be “unraveling ancient scrolls once thought unreadable” [p.1]. However, to perhaps clarify matters and concentrate the mind, the US ‘Department of Defense’ has been renamed as the ‘Department of War’ [3].

Biden

It seems that Joe Biden lives on in the mind of Donald Trump. Joe Biden is the only individual singled out for mention in the Action Plan. “President Trump rescinded the Biden Administration’s dangerous actions on day one” [p.1]. “The United States needs to ... dismantle unnecessary regulatory barriers ... restricting AI development with onerous regulation” [p.1]. “To maintain global leadership in AI, America’s private sector must be unencumbered by bureaucratic

red tape. President Trump has already ... [rescinded] Biden Executive Order 14110 on AI that foreshadowed an onerous regulatory regime” [p.3].

China

China is the only foreign country singled out for mention in the Action Plan. China is mentioned in each of the three Pillars of the AI Plan.

In Pillar I, US agencies are charged to “publish evaluations of frontier models from the People’s Republic of China for alignment with Chinese Communist Party talking points and censorship” [p.4] (whatever that means).

In Pillar II: “American energy capacity has stagnated since the 1970s while China has rapidly built out their grid. America’s path to AI dominance depends on changing this troubling trend” [p.14].

In Pillar III there is a section “Counter Chinese Influence in International Governance Bodies” [p.ii]. We read that: “too many of these [international] efforts have advocated for burdensome regulations, vague ‘codes of conduct’ that promote cultural agenda that do not align with American values, or have been influenced by Chinese companies attempting to shape standards” [p.20].

Figure 1. America’s AI Plan for Global domination (July, 2025)

Adversaries

The AI Plan is littered with unidentified “adversaries”. Beware of “adversary AI systems” [p.22], “adversarial technology” [p.14], “adversary information” [p.15], “adversarial inputs” [p.18], “adversarial threats” [p.18], “adversarial example attacks” [p.18], and “adversarial robustness” [p.9] (n=19 mentions). The Plan is first and foremost unilateralist; it is not about cooperation (no mention).

Malicious actors

In Action-Plan-Land there are also “malicious actors” to beware of. The AI Plan declares that: “we must prevent our advanced technologies from being misused or stolen by malicious

actors” [p.2]. The US AI Conquistadors must be on guard against various: “malicious cyber actors” [p.12], “malicious deep fakes” [p.12], “malicious activities” [p.18], “malicious inputs” [p.18], “malicious behavior” [p.22], and “malicious customers” [p.23].

American values

US agencies are “to vigorously advocate for international AI governance approaches that ... reflect American values” [p.20]. They must “Ensure that Frontier AI Protects ... American Values” [p.ii]. The NIST Risk Management Framework is to be revised “to eliminate references to misinformation, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion, and climate change” [p.4]. “We need to ensure America has leading open models founded on American values. Open-source and open-weight models could become global standards in some areas of business and in academic research worldwide. For that reason, they also have geo-strategic value” [p.4].

The White House view is that AI is not a value-free zone but rather a vehicle in which to embed ‘American values’. Just which ‘American values’ would they be? We may wonder just what the people in Vietnam, Afghanistan, Iraq, Venezuela, Gaza, Guantanamo Bay, and much of the rest of the world, think of ‘American values’?

Making America Intelligent Again?

The AI Plan of 2025 is more imperial than democratic, more conquistadorial than beneficent. It smacks of paranoia and megalomania. Indices suggest that the other AI, American Imperialism, is on a downward trajectory as the US has conceded the moral high ground, initiated decades of failed wars and military interventions, and persisted with political meddling in other countries’ affairs. Meanwhile, US society has fractures, with violent crime, poverty, illicit drugs, and homelessness blighting the country.

With its bombast of victory and global dominance, is the US grasping at the straws of decay? The US AI Plan adopts a win-lose stratagem, rather than a win-win one. But, AI is not a zero-sum game. World domination by USA may prove more malicious and pernicious, than benign. America’s AI Plan is a quest for maintaining an inequitable distribution of wealth and power, and concentrating them within a US empire.

Will Trump ‘Make America Great Again’ (MAGA)? Will he ‘Make America Intelligent Again’ (MAIA)? Is either possible? Is either desirable? Are both problematic? Time will tell.

The AI Plan is in pursuit of US domination and that must be a global concern. Similar past pursuits of, say, Genghis Khan, Napoleon, and Adolf Hitler, ended in tears.

Many will be hoping that India, China, the Middle East, South America, and others, can give America a ‘run for their money’ and that AI leadership is distributed rather than concentrated in the hands and pockets of a declining super power that presently treats even its loyal friends with disdain and arrogance [4-6].

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